

CONTROL IMPACT TESTING OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES WITH AND WITHOUT CARBON NANOTUBES OR SMA WIRES

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1 Introduction

Composite materials have been widely used in aerospace industry in the recent years due to their favorable properties such as high strength, stiffness, corrosion resistance, improved fatigue and light weight compared to metals. Despite these various advantages, one of the most important disadvantages of composite materials is that they have weak impact damage tolerance.

To improve the impact resistance of composite materials using SMA wires appears to have been investigated first by Paine and Rogers [1]. Many other potential benefits of SMA composites have been investigated since then, including the potential for SMA wires to improve the post-buckling response of composites, to improve the resistance to thermal buckling, and to modify the natural vibration frequency of composites [2]. For improving impact resistance, SMA wires have the capability of either imparting a compressive strain to a structure which can help to reduce the damage due to impact [3] or can assist in dissipating impact energy through superelasticity or pseudoelasticity ([1]; [4]).

Recent research showed that the use of shape-memory alloy (SMA) wires to absorb impact energy during the impact event improved the damage tolerance [5]. Strength, toughness, and transport (both electrical and thermal) of advanced composite materials are critically affected by the fiber/matrix and interlayer interface. The central issue under work on impact damage is how to minimize its effect on structural performance.

Nanotubes are used in a wide range of applications [6–7], but their mechanical, electronic and thermal properties make them ideal reinforcements of composite materials [8]. Nanotubes have high conductivity and high aspect ratio to produce conductive plastics with exceedingly low percolation thresholds [9]. Research showed that carbon nanotubes reinforced in carbon fibers give higher stiffness and strength [10]. Kostopoulos et al. impacted carbon fibers woven fabric specimens with CNTs and compared with specimens without CNTs and observed higher energy levels on specimens with CNTs [11].

2 Experimental Method and Results

2.1 Experimental Method

The material investigated in this current work is woven carbon fabric reinforced composite laminate, with an epoxy resin matrix. The fiber reinforcement was a Fibermax Composites C160P plain weave fabric. The composition of the resin was 100: 47 (by weight) of Fibermax Composites' epoxy resin 921 and 475524 hardener respectively. This resin can cure at room temperature.

To manufacture the composite panels, four layers of woven carbon fibers were used. The laminates were manufactured using an in-house wet lay-up process. A vacuum bagging kit from Fibermax Composites was used. First the resin was prepared by weighting

the epoxy resin and then slowly adding the hardener while stirring. The stirring of the mixture continued for a couple more minutes so that the resin would mix well with the hardener. Then, the first layer of carbon fiber was placed on the fabrication table and one quarter of the resin was evenly spread to wet the entire layer. On top of the first layer, the second layer of carbon fiber was carefully placed and was evenly wet with another quarter of the resin. This procedure continued for the remaining two layers of carbon fibers.

Above of the four layers a release fabric was placed covering them. The release fabric protects the laminate from the breath fabric and the vacuum bagging operations and also allows the excess epoxy to exit the laminate and can be easily peeled from the cured laminate. On top of that, the perforated film is placed. The perforated film helps hold the resin in the laminate when high vacuum pressure is used on thin laminates. The next step of the laminate fabrication is to place the breath fabric which provides a slight air space between the laminate and the vacuum bag. By using sealant tape, the vacuum bag is securely placed on top of the layers and is connected with a vacuum pump. The pump was turned on for about half an hour to ensure vacuum inside the bag. After ensuring that there were no leaks the pump was turned off and the laminate was left under vacuum over-night to cure.

Circular woven fabric panels of diameter 140 mm were cut from the resulting panels to be used as the impact specimens.

For the specimens with additional carbon nanotubes, CNTs from Rosseter Holdings Ltd were used. The CNTs were mixed with the hardener and were put in a magnetic stirrer and were left overnight to achieve higher dispersion. The next day the mixer of the hardener and the CNTs was slowly mixed with the epoxy resin. The procedure onwards is the same as with specimens without CNTs. The composite specimens with CNTs have an overall volume fraction of 2% of CNTs [12].

For the specimens with additional SMA wire reinforcement, superelastic shape-memory alloy wires (NiTi alloy S from Memory-Metalle GmbH, straight annealed, 0.152 mm diameter, Af

temperature of 0°C) were placed, between the last two woven glass fiber layers away from impact. The wires were manually wind on a frame (420 mm x 420mm) in both 0° and 90° direction (as shown in Figure 1) and then placed between the layers of woven fabric. The composite specimens having the SMA reinforcement had an overall wire volume fraction of about 2% of SMA.

A servo-hydraulic testing machine has been used, which enables the velocity of the impactor to be fixed during the experiment and the load to be recorded during a single impact event [1]. A servo-hydraulic testing machine was used for the impact testing. A video camera was used to monitor the experiment and record the sequence of damage of the specimens. Testing was carried out in displacement control using an actuator speed of 4 mm/sec for all the tests reported here, and both load and impactor displacement data were recorded.

The impact rig consists of a cage with the circular composite specimen clamped at the base of the cage. The cage is gripped in the upper grip of the servo-hydraulic testing machine (which is connected directly to the load cell, in the usual way). The circular impact specimens were clamped over an annulus of 20 mm, so that the area exposed for impact is a circular panel with a diameter 100 mm. A digital video camera, fixed within the cage, recorded the impact event. The impactor consisted of a glass sphere, 16 mm in diameter, mounted on a spigot.

The impact rig allows two related types of experiments to be carried out:

1. multiple impact and
2. single impact tests [1].

The first type is where the impactor is driven at constant velocity completely through the specimen (single impact test). Generally, this required an impactor displacement of about 24mm.

The second type of test is a multiple impact test. During a multiple impact test the impactor was driven at constant velocity into the specimen to a certain displacement e.g. 4mm from a datum where the impactor just contacted the specimen surface. Then, the impactor was withdrawn back to its initial position at the same velocity. The impactor was then driven to a higher displacement during the next impact i.e. 6mm and again returned to its initial position. For this process the increasing impactor displacements used during a multiple impact test were of 4 mm, 6 mm, 8 mm, 10 mm, 12 mm, 14 mm and 24 mm. By contrast, for the single impact test, the impactor displacement increased to 24 mm at constant velocity without interruption. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the servo-hydraulic testing machine indicating the impact rig and the impactor.

In the experiments described here, four layers of plain weave woven carbon fabric reinforcing epoxy resin, with and without carbon nanotubes or SMA wires, have been impacted. A digital video camera has enabled evolution of the damage to be recorded for comparison with the load/displacement data. Specimens subjected to a single and multiple impact tests (specimens with and without carbon nanotubes or SMA wires), at a constant impact velocity.

During the experiments the load was recorded as the displacement of the impactor increase and penetrated the specimens. Then, the load was plotted against the displacement and the energy needed to penetrate the specimens was calculated.

2.2 Results

Figure 3 shows typical load-displacement results for the single impact tests of three specimens with and without CNTs and SMA wires (specimens CFS07 - control, CNTS02 - CNTs and SMAS02 - SMAs). For the first 5mm into the specimens, specimens CNTS02 and SMAS02 are much stiffer than specimen CFS07, until the first macroscopic crack occurs where a sudden drop of load occurred. This sudden drop of load occurred at about 5.4mm for specimen CNTS02, 6.3mm for specimen SMAS02 and at about 6.4mm for specimen CFS07.

The peak loads of specimens CNTS02 and CFS07 occur at around same load (0.48kN for CNTS02 and 0.53kN for CFS07) where as the peak load of specimen SMAS02 occurred at a much higher load, around 0.66kN. After the peak load specimens CNTS02 and CFS07 decrease in load as the impactor moves further into the specimens with the specimen without CNTs decreasing faster than specimen with CNTs and completely penetrated at 17mm whereas the specimen with CNTs is penetrated at 24mm. In the contrary, after the peak load specimen SMAS02 increase in load up to 0.71kN and stayed in a constant range of load for about 6mm and then start decreasing at a constant rate to zero at around 22mm. This effect is due to the SMA wires where under load transform from austenite phase to stress-induced martensite phase by absorbing energy. As a result, the overall energy absorbed by the specimen with SMA is significantly higher (8.36J) than for the specimen with CNTs (5.55J) and specimens without CNTs or SMAs (3.30J). (Note: The increase of load found in the last millimeters is due to the impactor and is not counted in the energy absorption.)

A typical load-displacement plot for multiple impact tests of specimens with CNTs (specimen CNTM01) or SMAs (specimen SMAM03) and without CNTs or SMAs (specimen CFM02) is shown in Figure 4. For the first two cycles all specimens suffer little damage and the load-displacement hysteresis is small. For each subsequent cycle onwards the hysteresis increases as the damage on both specimens increase. Comparing the three specimens between them, similar results can be found as in specimens impacted with single impact test. Here as well the specimen with CNTs absorbed more energy (5.1J) than the specimen without CNTs (2.84J) but specimens with SMAs absorb much more energy than the other two specimens (8.55J).

The similarity in the load-displacement response for the single impact and multiple impact tests can be seen in Figure 5 where the responses are compared directly. Figure 5(a) shows the load-displacement response of two specimens, both with CNTs, one impacted as a single impact test (specimen CNTS05) and the second impacted as a multiple impact test (specimen CNTM02) [12]. In each case, the curves have matching initial stiffness and the overall shape

of the load-displacement response is approximately the same therefore the absorbed energies of the specimens are very similar (4.54J and 4.51J for single and multiple impact tests, respectively).

Similar results were found when comparing specimens without CNTs (Figure 5(b)), with absorbed energies of 3.35 J (single impact) and 3.31 J (multiple impact) [12].

Fig. 5(c) shows the load-displacement response for single (specimen SMAS06) and multiple impact tests (specimen SMAM01) of specimens with SMAs. It can be seen that both specimens have very similar initial stiffness and follow the same path up to the peak load. In both specimens the effect of wires is shown where the load is constant for few millimeters and then decrease with a constant rate to zero. Specimen SMAS06 (single impact) is fully penetrated at 22.6mm and specimen SMAM01 (multiple impact) very close just above 23mm. The specimens have very similar energy absorptions as well, 8.49J and 8.38J for specimens SMAS06 and SMAM01 respectively. This similar path between single and multiple impact tests were also seen when glass fiber woven fabric specimens with and without shape memory alloy wires were tested under control impact tests [1].

3. Discussion

Table 1 shows the average values of maximum Load, maximum displacement and energy for specimens with and without CNTs or SMA wires. The average values of the maximum load for specimens with and without CNTs are very similar (0.56kN and 0.51kN for specimens without CNTs and for specimens with CNTs, respectively). On the contrary, the average value of the maximum load for specimens with SMA wires is much higher, with about 27% increase, than the other two kinds of specimens (0.71kN). The average values of the maximum displacement that shows the displacement that the specimens were fully penetrated are very similar between the three kinds of specimens, 19mm for control specimens, 21mm for specimens with CNTs and 22mm for specimens with SMA wires.

Table 2 shows the average values of energy for specimens with and without CNTs or SMA wires, the difference in value from control specimens and the percentage increase of energy compared with control specimens. The results from previous work [12] show that the average energy absorption for specimens without CNTs is 3.36J whereas specimens with CNTs have average energy absorption of 4.42J. Therefore, an increase of about 1J can be seen, a noticeable 31.6% increase in energy absorption, for the specimens with CNTs.

Comparing the results of specimens with SMA wires from this work with the results of specimens without SMA wires a more remarkable increase in energy absorption can be seen. As mention above, the average energy absorption for control specimens is 3.36J whereas specimens with SMA wires have average energy absorption of 8.21J. As a result, an increase of almost 5J can be seen, which is converted to the remarkable 144% increase in energy absorption compared to control specimens and about 86% increase in energy absorption compared to specimens with CNTs.

4. Conclusions and Future work

4.1 Conclusions

As was seen before, multiple and single impact tests of similar type of specimens produce very similar results in terms of load-displacement behavior and energy absorption. The effect of SMA wires can be clearly seen in the load-displacement graph of specimens with 2% volume fraction SMA wire, after the peak load where the load stays at constant range for a few millimeters and then decrease at constant range to full penetration of the specimen. These specimens show a remarkable increase of 144% energy absorption compared to the control specimens (without CNTs or SMA wires) and a noticeable increase of 86% energy absorption when compared to the specimens with 2% volume fraction CNTs.

4.1 Future work

Further into the project a new hybrid composite with CNTs and SMA wires will be fabricated and impact tested. Their energy absorption will be compared with the specimens with and without CNTs or SMA wires. The specimens with both CNTs and SMA wires are expected to either show even higher increase in the energy absorption or the SMA wires will overpower the CNTs and the increase in energy absorption will remain at around 144%.

5 Figures and Tables

5.1 Figures

Fig. 1. A schematic of the frame used to wind the wires.

Fig. 2. A schematic of the servo-hydraulic testing machine that was used for the impact testing.

Fig. 3. Load-displacement response for single impact specimens with SMA (SMAS02), or with CNTs (CNTS02) and without CNTs or SMAs (CFS07).

Fig. 4. Load-displacement response for multiple impact specimens with SMA (SMAM03), or with CNTs (CNTM01) and without CNTs or SMAs (CFM02).

Fig. 5(a). Load-displacement response for single and multiple impact of specimens with CNTs [12].

Fig. 5(c). Load-displacement response for single and multiple impact of specimens with SMAs.

Fig. 5(b). Load-displacement response for single and multiple impact of specimens without CNTs [12].

5.2 Tables

Type of Specimens	Average Max. Load (kN)	Average Max. Displacement (mm)	Average Energy (J)
Control	0.56	19	3.36
With CNTs	0.51	21	4.42
With SMA	0.71	22	8.21

Table 1. Average values of maximum Load, maximum displacement and Energy for specimens with and without CNTs or SMA wires.

Type of Specimen	Average Energy (J)	Difference from Control (J)	Increased from Control (%)
Control	3.36	-	-
With CNTs	4.42	1.06	31.6
With SMA	8.21	4.85	144

Table 2. Average values of energy for specimens with and without CNTs or SMA wires, the difference in value from control specimens and the percentage increase of energy compared with control specimens.

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